

**RESEARCH THEME: "A COMPREHENSIVE LOOK AT THE EUROPEAN EARTH
OBSERVATION INDUSTRY: TRENDS, CHALLENGES, AND OPPORTUNITIES
FROM THE 2023 SURVEY"**

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Abstract

The data used in this article comes from the latest available 2023 European Association of Remote Sensing Companies (EARSC) survey and the purpose of this article is to present an overview of the state of the European EO industry. This paper outlines the key development in the area, which saw the sector record a 7.5% compounded annual growth rate over the last five years, with expected revenues of €1.79 billion in 2022. This growth shows the importance of the EO industry in meeting major world challenges, which include climate change, urbanization, and resource management through the development of new satellite data products. The survey also underlines the crucial role of the sector in view of the new EU and global context defined by the European Green Deal and the pledge of reaching climate neutrality by 2050. The article, through the mapping of the companies, employment patterns, and the role of the Copernicus program establishes the industry within the domains of Porter's Competitive Advantage and the Resource Dependency Theory while providing understanding of the industry's innovation potential as well as its weaknesses. Based on the analysis of the current development of the industry and the challenges identified, policy recommendations are proposed to promote sustainable development.

Keywords: Earth Observation, European EO Industry, EARSC Survey 2023, Satellite Data, Industry Growth, Copernicus Program, Policy Recommendations, Competitive Advantage, Resource Management, Climate Neutrality.

Introduction

The European EO industry is in the middle of a technology frontier and global needs, becoming a key enabler for climate change, environment and security policies. The EO sector, which uses satellite data, offers important information that helps decision-makers and society as a whole in areas such as development of cities, management of resources or response to crises. Increased awareness of climate change and changing geopolitical environment makes EO services more important than ever.

The 2023 European Association of Remote Sensing Companies (EARSC) Industry Survey is a comprehensive assessment of the current and future status of this fast-growing industry based on the input of more than 700 companies. Over the last five years, the industry has been growing at a compounded annual growth rate of 7.5% which translates to 2022 revenues of €1.79 billion, and a workforce of 13,929 employees. These statistics not only depict the contribution of the sector towards the economy but also depict the sector in line with other European targets including the Green Deal and the climate neutrality by 2050 (EARSC, 2023).

This article looks at the trends, challenges and opportunities within the EO industry through the lens of the 2023 survey. Discussed are the size and economic impact of the industry, the structure of the industry in terms of company types, employment pattern, market potential, and

Copernicus’s impact. Appreciating these findings within the lenses of Porter’s Competitive Advantage model and Resource Dependence Theory, the discussion articulates the sector’s opportunities and risks within the innovation ecosystem.

Standing at the heart of technological and geopolitical change, EO industry can become the solution to the major environmental and security issues troubling Europe. Nonetheless, to continue this growth path, every party in the ecosystem must play their part. This article aims at providing an understanding of these dynamics to help the industry understand its challenges and opportunities.

1. Growth and Economic Scale of the EO Industry (500 words)

Figure 1: Overview of this year’s industry survey

The European EO market has shown rapid development and is considered as an essential tool to solve many environmental, economic, and geopolitical issues. The most recent industry survey prepared by the EARSC for 2023 indicated that the sector generated a high annual revenue growth rate of 10.9%, resulting in a total revenue of €1.79 billion. In the past five years alone, the industry has had a CAGR of 7.5% indicating the industry’s flexibility and strength especially in light of the ever changing market and the global environment (EARSC, 2023).

With this survey, 772 EO companies were found to be based in 32 European countries, which is 3.5% more than in the previous year. The number of people also engaged in the sector also surged to 13,796 from 2022; an increase of 14.2% from the previous year. This growth supports other European Union priorities, including the goal of attaining climate neutrality by 2050 in accordance with the Green Deal and increasing space security through satellite intelligence (EARSC, 2023). The competitive advantage model by Porter (1990) reflects this trend by showing how the European investment in infrastructure, development and cooperation has cemented the region’s role in EO.

Since EO industry builds on the concept of integration with other applications, its growth is directly linked with its adoption in mainstream systems. The Green Deal that focuses on achieving the goal of carbon neutrality is mostly dependent on EO data for tracking emissions, forests management, and climate change measures. Likewise, the EU’s Strategic Compass for Security and Defence also underlines the role of EO in protecting space infrastructure assets and/or underpinning independent decision making. These applications are not only examples of the industry’s flexibility, but also of its ability to create significant economic and social returns.

But there are some problems associated with the growth of this industry. The expansion of the use of open data, especially from the Copernicus program, has implications for the business

models that depend on charging for their data. Copernicus data is the foundation of many EO services, but open data policy in Copernicus puts private companies that provide similar services under pressure. This situation is consistent with the tenets of Resource Dependence Theory developed by Pfeffer and Salancik (1978) which states that organisations that depend on external resources must manage their resource interdependence in order to survive.

As an economic resilience, the EO industry has proven its flexibility in handling disruptions through its response to political shift and technological evolution. Financial support for research and development has been secured through investments including the €16.9 billion promised by the 2022 Ministerial Council of the European Space Agency (ESA). These investments drive the growth of cutting-edge satellite systems and big data systems, which help the sector to compete with others on the global market.

2. Distribution and Classification of Companies

Figure 3: Breakdown of companies by company class

This paper explores the European EO industry which is made up of a large number of companies which are diverse in their operations. The 2023 EARSC Industry Survey shows that micro and small enterprises constitute 92-93% of all EO enterprises. Micro-enterprises, those companies that employ less than 10 workers, account for 35.2% of the sector, which underlines the role of small and mediumsized firms in developing technological innovation and market solutions (EARSC, 2023).

The high concentration of micro and small enterprises is consistent with the theory of disruptive innovation by Christensen (1997) arguing that small firms are much more capable of innovating in new markets. Such firms can easily adopt new technologies like Artificial intelligence and machine learning in EO services. But they face some constraints mainly

onResources and Operational Capacity in especially the aspects of scaling up operations and maintaining market competitiveness in a highly globalized environment.

Broken down by country, the survey data shows that the UK is the most popular destination for EO companies with 107 firms, while Germany ranks second with 100, and France third with 82 firms. They have been at the forefront of EO activity owing to availability of research infrastructure, sources of funding, and an enabling policy environment. Nevertheless, inequalities in the employment structure show that, although the greatest number of firms is based in the UK, Germany and France are leaders in the total number of employed people, suggesting that companies are, on average, larger in these countries (EARSC, 2023).

SMEs' dominance in EO industry evidence the important role of SMEs as the key drivers of innovation. Small and micro enterprises are more likely to be focused on leading-edge technologies, and create tailor-made solutions for specific segments of the market. As per Porter's (1990) Competitive Advantage model, this specialization helps SMEs to create competitive advantage over big companies especially in higher value added products or services like satellite image interpretation, geospatial data management and environmental surveillance.

Although SMEs have certain advantages over other organizations, the latter still have many problems concerning their expansion. According to the resource dependence theory by Pfeffer & Salancik, (1978) small firms face the challenge of accessing important resources such as capital, human Resource and market inputs. The survey identifies these issues, pointing out that micro-enterprises are especially threatened by publicly funded organizations that provide free or inexpensive EO data. Furthermore, due to the fact that EO has numerous applications across agriculture, defense, and urban planning, the market is highly fragmented, which makes it challenging for new entrant companies to enter and expand in the market.

To overcome these barriers the stakeholders in the industry together with the government must ensure that there are support systems for the SMEs. Programs on regional capacity building that are encouraged under the EU's Smart Specialization Strategy can assist in this respect in order to create more equity by developing innovation systems in regions that are often excluded. In addition, they are able to improve the accessibility of SMEs to some common resources and facilities, including data processing centers and cloud services that can help SMEs minimize operational costs when expanding.

3. Employment Trends and Skills Gaps

Employment Evolution:

The total number of employees in the sector in 2022 is 13,796 which represents a **growth rate of 14.2% over the last 12 months.**

Figure 7: Breakdown of Employees per company class

The European Earth Observation (EO) industry workforce has expanded considerably in the last year, with 13,796 people working in the sector in 2022, up 14.2% from the previous year (EARSC, 2023). This growth can therefore be attributed to the increasing importance of EO services in fields such as climate, infrastructural development and defense. Nevertheless, the industry still has certain human resource-related problems, especially the difficulty of attracting and retaining talent in technical positions.

In the EO sector, SMEs contribute 73% of total employment, which means that they play a very important part in employment generation and innovation. Nevertheless, these companies reveal the following challenges to recruiting, 77% of the firms surveyed said that they faced challenges in finding qualified employees. The major issues include the scarcity of talents in programming, data analytics and artificial intelligence (AI), and the problem of retraining of the workforce for EO related roles. These findings are in accord with the skills gap theory that explains the misfit between educational outcomes and labor market requirements (Acemoglu & Autor, 2011).

Of the skills needed, programming/development was considered most challenging to find, with 40% of companies responding that it was difficult for them to find such talent. This divide has been widened by the speed at which AI and machine learning have been incorporated into EO processes, as organizations need individuals who can handle these systems and deal with large volumes of data. This trend is in line with the general increase in the use of data analysis for decision making; as postulated by the theory of technological evolution (Nelson & Winter, 1982). Lack of such people is a major challenge to the growth of the industry and its ability to expand and be creative.

Geographical disparities also affect the employment situation. Germany and France are the most involved with 2,832 and 2,104 employees accordingly. However, the small markets experience a problem in recruiting professionals, especially in a locality with fewer job opportunities and sources. This discrepancy is perhaps the best argument for regional capacity-

building initiatives that can help alleviate labour deficiencies and support inclusive economic development.

The EARSC survey also outlines new trends such as the increasing needs for transversal skills in market analysis and customer relationship management. These skills are critical in the EO industry because it is shifting a focus towards customers and how its technology can meet their demands. As put forward by Kotler (1997) in the marketing mix model, good customer engagement entails accurate recognition of market conditions and users’ needs. The absence of these skills in the workforce is considered as the major constraint of EO solutions in the market.

In order to meet these challenges, a combination of measures is necessary. This paper has identified how collaboration between academia and industry can assist with ensuring that educational content is relevant as per the requirements of the EO sector. For instance, incorporating EO-specific modules within the engineering and data science degrees ensures that the graduates are prepared with the technical and analysis skills that the employers are looking for. Furthermore, government-led reskilling can create a more flexible workforce which can easily transfer to new positions as the EO technologies expand.

4. Market Opportunities and Challenges

Figure 18: Companies' main areas of activity in 2022

The European EO industry is a dynamic one, with new opportunities co-existing with long-standing issues. According to data from the 2023 EARSC Industry Survey, the center of gravity of the market remains with satellite operations occupying 32% of the sector’s activities while value added services trails slightly behind at 27%. This distribution is characteristic of the increasing

need for EO data and service in areas such as defense, agriculture, environment and so on (EARSC, 2023).

The EO industry has various uses across different markets, and there is a significant increase in the African and South American markets. These regions increased from 3% and 2% to 5% of the surveyed companies' activities last year. The expansion into these markets is informed by rising needs to address climate risks, disasters, and better resource utilization. This is in line with the global increasing focus on Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) where EO technologies are instrumental in monitoring and evaluation of the achievements and the challenges.

The defense and agricultural sectors have been identified as the most important growth enablers. Defence uses EO data and is backed up by the EU's Strategic Compass for Security and Defence to monitor, gather intelligence and make decisions. On the other hand, agriculture uses satellite imagery for precision farming, crop and resource management. Following Porter's (1990) value chain model, these applications augment competitive advantage by incorporating EO capabilities with downstream analyses to produce valuable information for the end-users.

Nevertheless, the industry has several obstacles in the way of achieving market acceptance. More than half of the companies surveyed identified user awareness and market acceptance as their major problem. This concurs with Rogers' (1962) Diffusion of Innovation Theory that postulates that a large number of potential users are still in the "early adopter" phase, and therefore, reluctant to incorporate EO technologies fully into their operations. This view of EO solutions as difficult to implement or as complementary to other systems hampers the uptake of the solutions.

There is the competition with other public entities that provide EO data, either for free or at a relatively low cost, as another challenge. The free-of-charge approach of the Copernicus program, on the one hand, fosters innovation, on the other hand, it poses a market threat to private companies interested in charging for similar services. Resource Dependency Theory (Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978) also captures this problem because private providers are dependent on public sources of data, which makes it hard for them to generate revenue.

This study also identifies high costs of EO technology and data acquisition as a factor that hinders market expansion, especially for SMEs. The survey concludes that the greatest challenge is the cost of the hardware and software as well as the data collection systems needed to implement the solution. This is in concurrence with the agency costs particularly capital costs as postulated by Jensen and Meckling (1976).

In order to overcome these barriers, the EO industry has to go for a well-coordinated, systematic effort. With a proper marketing strategy to promote the use of EO products and proper user education, the problems that result from EO technology awareness can be solved. Kotler's (1997) marketing mix model suggests that promotion strategies should target real life applications and returns in order to turn leads into loyal users.

Public private partnerships can also be used to effect change in costs and innovation. Through partnering with governmental institutions, private EO companies can get cheap inputs for example data platforms and training for SMEs. It also remains possible that regional incentives including grants and tax holidays will help firms enter unsaturated markets like Africa and South America.

5. Copernicus's Role and Future Outlook

The Copernicus program thus continues to be one of the most important assets of the European EO market, delivering the information and tools that fuel product development and commercial opportunity. According to the 2023 EARSC Industry Survey, the program has embraced the free and open data policy that has made it easy for companies to access quality satellite imagery for different uses. Nevertheless, this policy also brings some difficulties to private providers that try to generate revenues from EO services in the market (EARSC, 2023).

It is striking that all surveyed companies use Copernicus data, with 75% having a high usage of Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2, and active engagement with newer data from Sentinel-3 and Sentinel-5P. These resources support applications in agriculture, forestry, and urban monitoring providing evidence of the programs applicability to current world issues. The Green Deal and EU climate neutrality goals are supported by the Copernicus data to inform on emissions, assess the state of biodiversity and to inform on resource management.

The program's open data policy reflects Samuelson's (1954) public goods theory: it is stated that resources that are available for everyone bring positive external effects to society and economy. Through opening up of the access Copernicus stimulates innovations and mostly among the SMEs who cannot afford buying the exclusive data. However, the same policy creates an anticompetitive barrier to entry for private firms trying to provide new, unique services based on these same datasets.

The utilisation of Copernicus data poses important questions about the economic viability of the private sector revenue models. In the Resource Dependence Theory by Pfeffer and Salancik (1978), organizations with high dependence on external resources have to formulate responses to threats. The problem for private companies offering EO services is how best to add value to the data derived from the Copernicus program and how to position themselves in the face of free services provided by public agencies.

This problem is compounded by competition from public sector entities and other open access platforms. According to the survey, 55% of companies reported market acceptance as the most critical challenge and this is because of customers' preference of low-cost or free solutions. Furthermore, private providers have problems with explaining their prices in the market where top level data can be obtained for free. Such dynamics require new business models and cooperation to guarantee financial viability.

Further advancing, the Copernicus programme is expected to continue growing thanks to the new Sentinel missions, including CHIME (Copernicus Hyperspectral Imaging Mission) and LSTM (Land Surface Temperature Monitoring). These missions are anticipated to supply important information for the agriculture, forestry, and urban planning fields, thus increasing the application of the program. The participating companies indicate a high level of interest in these missions given that many of them see them as providing the opportunity to tap into new markets and increase revenues.

Moreover, Copernicus is an important contributor to Europe's digital agenda. Combining this data with those from future missions along with the use of analytics and artificial intelligence, the program can enable higher value applications including efficient farming and climate change impact assessment. These developments are consistent with Nelson and Winter's (1982) evolutionary theory of economic change where technology innovation is a key driver of industrial change.

Thus, in order to make full use of the potential of the Copernicus program with regard to the mentioned problems a joint approach of all parties interested should be considered. This paper will recommend the following policies that can help policymakers strengthen the role of private providers: Subsidies, tax incentives, and public-private partnerships that promote new ideas and methods. To add, companies can also use data integration platforms and cloud-based solutions in a bid to get more out of the Copernicus dataset.

This analysis also shows that educating the end-users about the benefits of value-added services can assist in closing the gap between the public and private sectors. Real world applications and practical uses that can be easily understood should be well explained in order to foster market uptake. Porter's (1990) Competitive Advantage model also recognizes the role of differentiation in the competitive and resource based market environment to achieve competitive edge.

6. Policy and Investment Needs for the EO Industry

The future and impact of the European EO industry's development and achievements in the pursuit of essential societal objectives depends on secure policies and strategic funding. The marker, according to the 2023 EARSC Industry Survey, the EO sector is situated in the convergence of technology advancement and the issues of the world today like climate change, security, and sustainable development. Nevertheless, to reach its full possibilities, the industry needs specific measures to overcome the challenges related to the lack of funding, minimal venture capital, and inadequate infrastructure (EARSC, 2023).

Another vital achievement in enhancing the EO industry was the €16.9 billion commitment from the ESA's 2022 Ministerial Council. This marks an increase of 17 % from the 2019 commitment which shows that Europe is serious about the development of space technologies and EO applications. These funds help fund critical activities, including the expansion of new Sentinel missions and data integration systems that help strengthen the industry and its ability to create new products and services.

From a theoretical framework, the framework of Porter's Competitive Advantage model (1990) greatly emphasizes the role of infrastructure investments in industry development. Specialized funding programs, for instance ESA's Space for a Green Future accelerator, prove that the right capital can help EO firms support strategic objectives like the Green Deal and the digital agenda. These programs are not only an improvement on current technologies but also open doors for cooperation between public and private sectors.

However, one of the biggest issues to this date is the question of funding, especially for SMEs in the EO industry. The research shows that 55% of the companies have issues with venture capital and others cannot get loans or equity investments either. This finding is in consonance with the agency theory advanced by Jensen and Meckling in 1976 whereby the financial consequences of seeking external finance are discussed. To the best of the authors' knowledge, a major constraint that can restrict innovation and market entry in EO, as well as other capital-intensive domains, is the shortage of funds available to SMEs.

Policy makes should, therefore, focus on ways of increasing the flow of funds to EO companies. The use of tax exemptions, grants, and co-investment can help private sector engagement and alleviate the fiscal pressure on SMEs. Also, there is a need to link EO companies with IFIs for them to get access to other sources of funding. According to the survey, organizations

that received IFI funding from organizations like the World Bank or a regional development bank are in a vantage position to expand their operations and enter the international market.

The free and open data policy of the Copernicus program is a boon and bane for the EO industry. Although this policy opens up access to top-notch datasets for everyone it presents challenges to private companies that seek to charge for similar services. To this end, government should probably think about adopting the tiered data access approach that allows commercial use of the data with added value while keeping the data open to the public.

Additionally, funding of data-sharing platforms and cloud-based applications can increase the applicability and expandability of EO data. These initiatives are consistent with Isenberg's (2011) entrepreneurial ecosystem framework as these require infrastructure to support innovation and collaboration. Through enhancing the access to EO data, the policymakers can help both the public and private entities to achieve more from the EO data.

The future success of the EO industry also depends on the solution of the long-standing problem of human resources shortage. The survey reveals that the existing workforce lacks in some areas such as programming, data analytics and Artificial intelligence. To address this gap, government-led reskilling programs in cooperation with academic and business institutions should be developed to make the output of educational institutions meet the needs of the market. Also, specific immigration policies may be used to lure talent to fill the vacancies in the workforce at the current time.

Following Nelson and Winter's (1982) evolutionary theory of economic change, it can be argued that labour flexibility is essential for industries that exist in contexts with fast changing technological dynamics. The author argues that through training and development, EO industry will be well equipped to face any future challenges that may come its way.

As such, coordination between governments and other stakeholders, private sector and international organizations is crucial for the development of a sustainable EO system. The public private partnerships offer opportunities to pool resources, joint ventures and co-innovation to allow companies to expand their reach and expand their business into new territories. For instance, common assets like data center and communication satellites can provide SMEs with relief from certain operating costs and also increase the productivity of the entire sector.

It should also promote the provision of supportive policy frameworks that would foster the international cooperation in the expansion of European EO firms. Strategies that support the export-based growth, including trade delegations, and the business-to-business platforms, enable firms to gain entry into new markets in Africa and South America. Such efforts are in conformity with Porter's (1990) cluster theory where he stated that industries depend on regional and global networks to compete.

CONCLUSION

The 2023 EARSC Industry Survey paints a picture of the European EO industry as a vital player in meeting the world's challenges and advancing change. The sector has recorded a sensational five-year compound annual growth rate of 7.5% and is expected to generate €1.79 billion in revenue in 2022. However, its future success remains a function of how it will avoid or manage risks that have persisted over the years while exploiting new trends.

Some of the features identified from the survey include: The fact that the industry is dominated by SMEs because 92% of the companies in the industry are SMEs while SMEs account

for 73% of employment. These organizations are the core of innovation that involve innovative technologies and services in areas like agriculture, defense, and climate change. However, their resource constraints and capacities show that they require special assistance to increase their scale and sustainability.

The place of Copernicus in this context is critical as it provides free and open data to support innovation. The Copernicus data serves the basis of many applications, ranging from agriculture to decision making in cities. However, this open access model creates problems for private actors interested in delivering distinctive and chargeable services. Resource Dependence Theory as propagated by Pfeffer and Salancik (1978) provides a background on the importance of the management of these dependencies to guarantee long period of existence.

Unemployment and skills mismatch are still the biggest challenges that hinder development. There is high competition in the market for programming, data, and artificial intelligence, saving the potential for growth. To meet this challenge, ParserGap

Potential markets in Africa and South America may become new horizons for the company's development. Nonetheless, there are challenges that need to be overcome in order to realize these opportunities including market challenges, competition from publicly funded organizations, and costs of EO technologies. The new challenges identified in Porter's Competitive Advantage model (1990) include differentiation and collaboration approaches in managing these challenges.

For the EO industry to continue its upward growth trend, there is the need to reinvest in infrastructure, people, and data. This means that public private partnerships, international cooperation and enablement policies can help build a system that will be able to sustain innovation and growth. The €16.9 billion proposed by the European Space Agency (ESA) is evidence that Europe is serious about the development of the EO sector and strategic objectives of the EU Green Deal and climate neutrality by 2050.

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